

Simple and sensitive RP-HPLC/RID method for the determination of triclofos sodium

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Abstract : A simple and sensitive RP-HPLC method was developed and validated for the determination of triclofos sodium in oral solution using 'Watman' Partisil SCX (250×4.6 mm, 5 μm) with a mobile phase of 0.01% formic acid buffer with pH 3.5 with a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min (RI detection). The proposed method provided linear responses within the concentration range 0.25–0.75 mg/mL for triclofos sodium. Correlation coefficient (*r*) of the regression equation was greater than 0.999. The optimized method was validated with respect to specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision and robustness.

Keywords : Triclofos sodium, oral solution, HPLC-RID.

Introduction

Triclofos sodium (TS), chemically known as [sodium 2,2,2-trichloroethyl hydrogen orthophosphate], shown in Fig. 1, is a sedative drug used for the short term relief of severe insomnia.

Fig. 1. Chemical name of triclofos sodium.

Literature survey reveals that there are several liquid chromatographic methods^{1,2} and titration^{3,4} methods reported for the triclofos sodium. The chemical methods (titration) are too complex, and involve many steps to determine the target molecule.

The present research work describes the quantitative determination of triclofos sodium in oral solution by using RP-HPLC with refractive index detector (RID) method. This is a simple, rapid test method and provides accurate and precise test results. Refractive index detector is a versatile technique and can be used for the analysis of non-chromophoric compounds. The objective of this work is to avoid the intricacy of the sample preparation, and

develop a user and environment friendly test method for triclofos sodium.

Experimental

Chemicals :

Triclofos sodium standard and pedicloryl oral solution (triclofos sodium, 500 mg/5 mL, w/v) were kindly supplied by Dr. Reddy's Laboratories Ltd., India. Formic acid (AR grade) and sodium hydroxide (AR grade) were purchased from Merck, India. Water (HPLC grade) was obtained from Milli-Q Plus water purification system (Millipore, Bedford, USA).

Equipment :

Waters HPLC-RI system consists of a binary solvent manager (Waters 1525 binary HPLC pump), a sample manager (Waters 717 plus auto sampler) and a RI detector (Waters 2414 refractive index detector). The output signal was monitored and processed using empower software. The detector is equipped with mobile phase at 30 °C detector temperature, 64 of its sensitivity, and positive (+) polarity. RI detector is stabilized for about one hour for getting neat and stable base line.

Chromatographic conditions :

The separation was achieved on 'Watman' Partisil SCX,

250×4.6 mm, i.d with 5 µm particles in isocratic elution. The mobile phase contains a mixture of pH 3.5, 0.1 mL formic acid in 1000 mL of HPLC grade water.

The flow rate of mobile phase was 0.5 mL/min. The RI detector sensitivity was selected as 64 for getting good response of main analyte. The detector temperature maintained at 30 °C, the run time of the chromatogram set as 14 min for eluting all the excipients peaks. The column temperature was maintained at 40 °C and the detection was monitored with RID. The injection volume was 20 µL injected into HPLC-RID.

Preparation of standard solution :

A standard solution of triclofos sodium working standard (0.5 mg mL⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving an appropriate amount in diluent (a mixture of pH 3.5, 0.1 mL formic acid in 1000 mL of HPLC grade water) for assay determination (Fig. 2).

Preparation of sample solution :

Pedicaleryl oral solution (triclofos sodium) 500 mg/5 mL, v/v (each 1-mL contains 100 mg of triclofos sodium). One (1) mL of solution which contains 100 mg of triclofos sodium is weighed and transferred to a 100-mL volumetric flask. The drug was finally dissolved in 100 mL of diluent. Test solution (0.5 mg/mL) was prepared

from above diluent for assay determination. The solution was filtered through 0.45 µm Millipore PVDF disk filter. The retention time of triclofos sodium was found to be 4.17 min (Fig. 3).

Method development and optimization :

The proposed method was optimized by considering the below mentioned separation goals, they are detector, HPLC column, column temperature and detector temperature, and mobile phase.

Selection of detector :

RI detector is used due to non-chromophoric nature of the molecule. Non-chromophoric compounds can be also estimated by using FID (GC)/ELSD/CAD or other if any. RI detector is only used due to the unavailability of other detectors.

Evaluation of HPLC column :

Different experimental trials have been conducted for column selection. Different kinds of stationary phases (columns) such as X-Terra RP18 : 250×4.6 mm, 5 µm, Inertsil ODS : 250×4.6 mm, 5 µm, Allysep Anion : 150×4.6 mm, 5 µm, Hypersil BDS C₁₈ : 250×4.6 mm, 5 µm, and 'Watman' Partisil SCX, 250×4.6 mm, 5 µm, were used to find out the suitable column. Finally, 'Watman' Partisil SCX, 250×4.6 mm, i.d with 5 µm

Fig. 2. Triclofos sodium standard chromatogram.

Fig. 3. Triclofos sodium sample chromatogram.

particles (strong cation exchange) column was selected and a good separation was achieved from the placebo peaks. Formic acid was added to the mobile phase to inhibit the peak tailing which caused by residual silanol interactions. The concentration of formic acid in mobile phase was optimized to 0.01% while maintaining the buffer pH at 3.5.

Selection of mobile phase :

pH 3.5 formic acid (0.01%) buffer is selected as mobile phase which gave a sharp peak at the retention time of about 4.2 min. Organic modifiers (such as acetonitrile/methanol) are not used in the mobile due to closely eluting peaks of placebo solution. However, the best separation is achieved with only the buffer solution.

Evaluation of column temperature and detector temperatures :

The column temperature is selected as 40 °C. The effect of column temperature is evaluated using high temperature, however no impact on the retention time of the triclofos sodium. The detector temperature is selected as 40 °C to get a neat and stable base line.

Selection of retention time :

Interference of excipients was evaluated by injecting sample solutions of all the excipients. There was no inter-

ference existed with the excipients which are used in the formulation of pedicloryl oral solution. TS peak is eluted at about 4.2 min and well separated from the excipients peaks. So, the total run time of the chromatogram is selected as 14 min.

Method validation :

The proposed method was validated as per ICH Q2 (1) guidelines^{5,6}.

Precision :

The precision of assay was determined by analyzing six replicate assay samples of triclofos sodium (0.5 mg/mL) against the qualified and valid working standard. Different analysts from the different laboratories were evaluated the intermediate precision of the method. The percentage of assay of triclofos sodium was calculated and the results meet the requirements. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Linearity :

The linearity was established in the concentration range of 0.25 mg/mL to 0.75 mg/mL which covered from 50 to 150% of target concentration. The working standard stock solution was diluted with mobile phase and prepared the individual linearity solutions. Each linearity solution was analyzed using the HPLC.

Peak areas (y) of TS were plotted against the respec-

Table 1. Results of precision study

Spl. No.	Repeatability	Intermediate precision
1	100.7	100.2
2	101.9	100.6
3	101.2	100.8
4	102.5	101.3
5	101.3	102.4
6	101.1	99.9
Mean	101.5	100.9
%RSD	0.6	0.9

tive concentration (x) and linear regression analysis was performed on the resultant calibration curves. The linearity result shows that an excellent correlation existed between the peak area and concentration of the analyte. The regression coefficient (R^2) value found to be 0.9979 (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Linearity of triclofos sodium.

Accuracy :

The accuracy of the test method was conducted at five different concentration levels ranging from 50 to 150% of the target sample concentration (0.5 mg/mL) by spiking the TS on the placebo solution. The recoveries meet the requirements, ranging from 99.9 to 101.6% (Table 2). The regression analysis was performed for the accu-

Table 2. Results of accuracy study

Spike level (%)	Mean amount added (mg/mL)	Mean amount found (mg/mL)	% Mean recovery (n = 3)
50	245.1305	248.0002	101.2
75	364.0424	369.9766	101.6
100	485.4434	484.7764	99.9
125	602.6693	603.8186	100.2
150	726.5593	739.3306	101.8

racy of test method and the correlation coefficient, R^2 , was found to be 0.9994 (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Linearity of test method (recovery study).

Specificity :

The specificity (placebo interference) of the test method was established by injecting placebo solution (without triclofos sodium) into an HPLC-RID. No interference was observed from all these adjuvants which are generally used in oral solution formulation. Carry over study was conducted by injecting the mobile phase after the repeatability sample (six) solution. No interference peaks were detected and no carry over was observed in blank solution. During the method specificity study, the run time of all chromatograms was extended to about 30 min. Based on the validation data, the run time of the chromatogram was shortened to 14 min. No unknown peaks were detected after 14 min (Fig. 6 and Fig. 7).

Solution stability and mobile phase stability :

The stability study was established for the sample and standard solutions by storing the solutions in tightly capped clear volumetric flasks for 48 h at ambient temperature, and were assayed at 24 h and 48 h against freshly prepared standard solution of TS. The percentage of RSD for the assay of TS was calculated and found to be within 2.5, and this indicates that the standard and sample solutions were stable for 2 days on bench top at ambient temperature.

The stability of mobile phase was also established by assaying the freshly prepared standard solution for 7 days

Fig. 6. Placebo chromatogram for specificity study.

Fig. 7. Blank chromatogram for specificity study.

interval up to 14 days. The mobile phase was stored in a clear glass bottle during this study. The percentage of RSD for assay of TS was calculated and was found to be within the limits (Limit : NMT 3.0).

Robustness :

To determine the robustness of the proposed test method, the experimental conditions were deliberately altered and the tailing factor, theoretical plate and retention time of TS were recorded. The flow rate of mobile phase was 0.5 mL/min, to study the effect of flow rate on the retention time, flow rate was changed by 0.1 mL/min

units, i.e. 0.4 and 0.6 mL/min. The effect of column temperature on retention time was studied at 35 °C and 45 °C instead of 40 °C. The effect of pH variation on retention time was studied by varying pH by ± 0.2 units. Due to variation in flow rate, column temperature and pH of the buffer, there is no major impact on the retention time, tailing factor and theoretical plates of TS peak.

Comparison with the traditional chemical method :

A comparison of the present method is made with the traditional chemical method and is given in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of the present method with the traditional chemical method

	Traditional chemical method (titration)	Present method
Selectivity		
Time	It is a multi-step process and also complicated process. It takes more than 5 h to prepare one sample solution.	It is a simple and a single step method. Takes 5 to 10 min to prepare one sample solution.
Environment	This method is an environmentally hazardous (i.e. silver nitrate). Many different kinds of chemicals and reagents are needed for the analysis, viz. sodium hydroxide, ether, sulphuric acid, isoamyl alcohol, alcoholic potassium hydroxide, nitric acid, silver nitrate, ammonium thiocyanate and ammonium iron(III) sulphate.	This method is friendly with an environment. Only two chemicals and reagents are needed for the analysis, viz. formic acid and sodium hydroxide.
Economy	Expensive due to the requirement of more cost effective chemical.	In-expensive (low-cost).

Conclusion

A simple and rapid RP-HPLC-RID method was developed and validated successfully for the determination of triclofos sodium in the oral solutions. In comparison with chemical (titration) methods, this method appears to be equally appropriate for routine testing of triclofos sodium in its formulations. The advantages of this method are short run time and a small amount of sample consumption, both of which significantly reduce the duration of the analysis. This method can be an excellent alternative for the chemical (titration) method.

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